

ENGAGEMENT AND COMPETENCE AMONG ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEVEL IN CLUSTER 4 DIVISION OF CALAMBA CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study's primary goal was to gauge the level of student engagement and competence among the Junior High School level learners within the Division of Calamba City. The study was quantitative research that employed a descriptive correlational approach with respondents of 120 learners from the different learning centers of Cluster 4 and 12 ALS teachers. The instruments used for data gathering were the Functional Literacy Test which was used for ALS learners and an adopted instrument for student engagement. The results revealed that many learners were at the beginning level when it comes to the following learning strands: Learning Strand 1 Communication Skills in English, LS1 Kasanayang Pagkatuto sa Filipino, LS2 Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills, LS3 Mathematics and Problem-Solving Skills, and LS6 Digital Citizenship. While in LS4 Life and Career Skills and LS5 Understanding the Self and the Society many learners were at the proficient and approaching proficient level. There was a significant relationship between student engagement and competencies based on the assessment of the learners and teachers of ALS. Based on the results, Proran PARESAN was recommended which will hopefully help learners develop not only the necessary skills and competence for their future endeavors but also to boost their confidence by showing their talents through the different programs included in the project being proposed.

Keywords: *student engagement, competencies, learners, Alternative Learning System*

INTRODUCTION

Global educational systems exhibit notable variations, notwithstanding the universal influence of certain factors, such as financial resources and human capital. The distribution of educational resources is a significant problem in many countries, including the US, where state-by-state variations in funding per student exist. Both official and informal educational systems facilitate the transmission of culture. The issue of universal access to education is global in scope. The destiny and identity of a country have been greatly influenced by its educational system due to the important role that this invaluable knowledge plays in promoting both national advancement and economic stability. The offering of outstanding education and a supportive learning atmosphere inspires Filipinos to advance their skills, knowledge, and inventiveness. By providing the Philippines' young children with access to top-notch education, we raise the country's standard of living while assisting in their professional development and preparation for global competition.

The Department of Education (DepEd) declared that 4 million children were not able to enroll for the current school year. Due to different circumstances in life, the number of out-of-school youths and adults increased. One of the largest second-chance education initiatives in the world was in the Philippines. The Alternative Learning System, or ALS, had 5.5 million adolescent and adult students 15 years of age and older enrolled in it over the previous ten years. The Department of Education received World Bank guidance on raising its performance standards. ALS was a successful second-chance program that helped its students, but it also needed to be continually improved to assist them in reaching their full potential. The Philippines' ALS experience was instructive for other nations going through a similar problem and student engagement was also a focus of the ALS (Gamboa, 2023)

Student engagement was the level of focus, participation, curiosity, enthusiasm, and hope that students exhibited. Students were more driven to learn and advance in their education the more involved they were in the classroom. It had been demonstrated that when students were curious, engaged, or inspired, their learning improved; when they were bored, uninspired, disengaged, or lacking in passion, their learning decreased. "Engaged Students" had an impact on how well students were taught and learned. Students were able to think critically and comprehend, analyze, and interpret situations more effectively (Chatti, 2021).

Meanwhile, the competence of ALS students is also another focus of the program. Competence refers to the competencies, information, and expertise that students acquire through their education. It encompasses both cognitive and practical skills necessary for academic success and future employment. Competent learners possess the necessary literacy, numeracy, and critical thinking skills required to navigate their educational journey and prepare for their desired careers. Understanding the level of competence among ALS junior high school level learners is vital to evaluate how well the program has prepared them with the required information and abilities.

As cited in Sukor et al. (2021), students' participation in successful educational activities both inside and outside of the classroom was correlated with their level of engagement in learning. Engaged students can improve their grades, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, as well as apply their learning in the workplace (Lee et al., 2019). Correlating student engagement and competence were relevant aspects to conduct considering their importance to learning.

This quantitative descriptive-correlational research aimed to determine the student engagement and competence level among ALS Junior High School learners. By conducting a systematic assessment of these aspects, the study intended to identify the engagement level of students in terms of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement. The proficiency of students in the various Alternative Learning System learning areas was also determined by the study. These aspects were needed to be determined especially for teachers like the researcher who are deeply concerned with their skills and competence.

Research Questions

1. What is the student engagement level among ALS junior high school level learners as assessed by teachers and students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Behavioral Engagement,
 - 1.2 Cognitive Engagement, and
 - 1.3 Emotional Engagement?
2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the teachers and students on student engagement level?
3. What is the competence level among ALS junior high school level learners in terms of:
 - 3.1 Communication Skills in English,
 - 3.2 Kasanayang Pangkomunikasyon sa Filipino,
 - 3.3 Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills,
 - 3.4 Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills,
 - 3.5 Life and Career Skills,
 - 3.6 Understanding the Self and the Society, and
 - 3.7 Digital Citizenship?
4. Is there a significant relationship between student engagement level and competence level among ALS Junior High School level learners in Cluster 4 Calamba City?
5. Based on the findings, what guidance program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted within the area of Cluster 4 of The Division of Calamba City. Under this cluster are the following barangays: Real, Turbina, Saimsim, Makiling, and Puting Lupa. The respondents to this study were composed of cluster 4's junior high school level

population. Whereas the sampling technique known as total enumeration was used. By engaging all learners as participants, the research can focus on obtaining a sample that is most relevant to the research question and can provide meaningful insights into the variations in student engagement and competence among ALS learners in Cluster 4 Division of Calamba City within a quantitative research framework. This study used two adopted instruments: The level of student engagement questionnaire and the ALS Functional Literacy Test. These two tests were known for complementing each other's results. In this study, a researcher-made questionnaire was used to gauge student engagement, and its reliability and validity were assessed using Cronbach's alpha. The updated Functional Literacy Test (FLT) aided in identifying any prior knowledge that a person may already possess. The first instrument was standard, but content validation was still applied to determine whether it was appropriate for the situation. Several adjustments were made to fit the language to the comprehension of the students. The researcher asked permission from the owner of the instrument through e-mail. The owner of the questionnaire responded quickly and gave consent to use the instrument to measure the student's engagement level. This descriptive correlational research focused on identifying the levels of student engagement and competence within the ALS program specifically at the Junior High School level of Cluster 4 in the Division of Calamba City.

RESULTS

Table 1.1

Student Engagement Level among ALS Junior High School Level Learners as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Behavioral Engagement

Indicators in terms of Behavioral Engagement	Teachers		Students		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Asked questions in class or contributed to class discussion.	3.27	HE	3.28	HE	3.28	HE	2
2. Raising my hand in class.	3.09	E	3.20	E	3.15	E	8.5
3. Participating in or small group discussions.	3.27	HE	3.48	SE	3.38	HE	1
4. Doing all the homework problems.	3.00	E	3.53	SE	3.27	HE	3.5
5. Coming to class every day.	2.82	E	3.61	SE	3.22	E	5
6. Taking good notes in class.	3.27	SE	3.26	SE	3.27	HE	3.5
7. Getting a good grade.	3.09	E	3.26	SE	3.18	E	7
8. Staying up on the readings.	2.91	E	3.18	E	3.05	E	11

9. Received prompt written or oral feedback from faculty on your academic performance.	3.18	E	3.11	E	3.15	E	8.5
10. Come to class without completing readings or assignments	2.18	NE	1.40	NE	1.79	SE	12
11. Making sure to study on a regular basis.	3.00	E	3.39	HE	3.20	E	6
12. Doing well on a test.	3.18	E	3.08	E	3.13	E	10
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.02	E	3.15	E	3.09	E	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Highly Engaged
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Engaged

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Engaged
1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Engaged

Table 1.2

Student Engagement Level among ALS Junior High School Level Learners as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Cognitive Engagement

Indicators in terms of Cognitive Engagement	Teachers		Students		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Made a class presentation	3.27	HE	3.26	HE	3.27	HE	4
2. Prepared two or more drafts of a paper or assignment before turning it in.	3.09	E	3.25	HE	3.17	E	9
3. Worked on a paper or project that required integrating ideas or information from previous sources.	3.09	E	3.13	E	3.11	E	11
4. Put together ideas or concepts from different courses when completing assignments or during class discussion.	3.18	E	3.28	HE	3.23	E	7
5. Used an electronic medium to discuss or complete an assignment.	2.91	E	3.13	E	3.02	E	14.5
6. Discussed ideas from readings or classes with faculty members outside of class.	3.09	E	3.15	E	3.12	E	10
7. Putting forth effort.	3.36	SE	3.59	HE	3.48	HE	1
8. Used e-mail to communicate with an instructor.	2.82	E	3.06	E	2.94	E	16
9. Discussed grades or assignments with an instructor.	3.00	E	3.09	E	3.05	E	13
10. Work harder than you thought you could do to meet an instructor's standards or expectations.	3.27	SE	3.47	HE	3.37	HE	2
11. Discussed ideas from your readings or classes with others outside of class.	3.00	E	3.16	E	3.08	E	12
12. Going to the professor's office hours to review assignments of tests, or to ask questions.	2.73	E	3.09	E	2.91	E	17

13. Thinking about the course between class meetings.	2.91	E	3.12	E	3.02	E	14.5
14. Finding ways to make the course interesting to me.	3.00	E	3.37	HE	3.19	E	8
15. Looking over class notes between classes to make sure I understand the materials.	3.18	E	3.31	HE	3.25	HE	5.5
16. Applying course materials to my life.	3.18	E	3.32	HE	3.25	HE	5.5
17. Finding ways to make the course relevant to my life.	3.09	E	3.47	HE	3.28	HE	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.07	E	3.25	HE	3.16	E	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Highly Engaged
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Engaged

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Engaged
1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Not Engaged

Table 1.3

Student Engagement Level among ALS Junior High School Level Learners as assessed by Teachers and Students in terms of Emotional Engagement

Indicators in terms of Emotional Engagement	Teachers		Students		Composite		Rank
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	
1. Included diverse perspective in class discussions or writing assignments.	3.09	E	3.21	E	3.15	E	8
2. Worked with other students on projects during class.	3.27	HE	3.37	HE	3.32	HE	4
3. Worked with classmates to prepare class assignments.	3.09	E	3.33	HE	3.21	E	6.5
4. Tutored or taught other students paid or voluntary.	3.09	E	3.14	E	3.21	E	6.5
5. Participated in a community-based project as part of a regular course.	3.00	E	3.17	E	3.09	E	10.5
6. Had serious conversations with students who are very different from you in terms of their religious, political opinions, or personal values.	3.27	HE	3.28	HE	3.28	HE	5
7. Really desiring to learn the materials.	3.27	HE	3.50	HE	3.39	HE	3
8. Being confident that I can learn and do well in the class.	3.27	HE	3.58	HE	3.43	HE	2
9. Having fun in class.	3.27	HE	3.66	HE	3.47	HE	1
10. Worked with faculty on activities other than course work.	3.27	HE	2.90	E	3.09	E	10.5
11. Talked about career plans with a faculty member or adviser	3.18	E	3.09	E	3.14	E	9

Table 3.2*Competence Level among Junior High School Level Learners in terms of Kasanayang Pangkomunikasyon sa Filipino*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Advanced	21	17.50%
85 – 89	Proficient	13	10.83%
80 – 84	Approaching Proficient	26	21.67%
75 – 79	Developing	16	13.33%
74 and below	Beginning	44	36.67%
Total		120	100%
Overall Performance		78.24	

Table 3.3*Competence Level among Junior High School Level Learners in terms of Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Advanced	11	9.17%
85 – 89	Proficient	25	20.83%
80 – 84	Approaching Proficient	9	7.50%
75 – 79	Developing	19	15.83%
74 and below	Beginning	56	46.67%
Total		120	100%
Overall Performance		72.58	

Table 3.4*Competence Level among Junior High School Level Learners in terms of Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Advanced	23	19.17%
85 – 89	Proficient	11	9.17%
80 – 84	Approaching Proficient	21	17.50%
75 – 79	Developing	21	17.50%
74 and below	Beginning	44	36.67%
Total		120	100%
Overall Performance		78.60	

Table 3.5*Competence Level among Junior High School Level Learners in terms of Life and Career Skills*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Advanced	66	55.00%
85 – 89	Proficient	17	14.17%
80 – 84	Approaching Proficient	20	16.67%
75 – 79	Developing	5	4.17%
74 and below	Beginning	12	10.00%
Total		120	100%
Overall Performance		86.68	

Table 3.6*Competence Level among Junior High School Level Learners in terms of Understanding the Self and Society*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Advanced	94	78.33%
85 – 89	Proficient	6	5.00%
80 – 84	Approaching Proficient	5	4.17%
75 – 79	Developing	7	5.83%
74 and below	Beginning	8	6.67%
Total		120	100%
Overall Performance		91.34	

Table 3.7*Competence Level among Junior High School Level Learners in terms of Digital Citizenship*

Grade	Indicators	F	%
90 – 100	Advanced	33	27.50%
85 – 89	Proficient	11	9.17%
80 – 84	Approaching Proficient	12	10.00%
75 – 79	Developing	21	17.50%
74 and below	Beginning	43	35.83%
Total		120	100%
Overall Performance		78.28	

Table 4

Test of Significant Relationship between Student Engagement and Competence among ALS Junior High School Level Learners in Cluster 4 Calamba City

Student Engagement	Competence	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Behavioral Engagement	Communication skills in English	.082	.187	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Communication skills in Filipino	.112	.112	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	.009	.462	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	.144	.058	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Life and Career Skills	.022	.406	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Understanding the Self and Society	.019	.421	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Digital Citizenship	.012	.448	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
Cognitive Engagement	Communication skills in English	.184**	.004	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Communication skills in Filipino	.122*	.048	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	.256**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	.138*	.033	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Life and Career Skills	.212**	.001	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Understanding the Self and Society	.263**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Digital Citizenship	.314**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Emotional Engagement	Communication skills in English	.029	.756	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Communication skills in Filipino	.026	.782	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills	.076	.411	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills	.072	.268	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Life and Career Skills	.040	.534	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Understanding the Self and Society	.016	.800	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Digital Citizenship	.043	.511	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the student engagement level among ALS junior high school level learners as assessed by teachers and students in terms of:

1.1 Behavioral Engagement

The ALS Junior High School students were **Engaged (3.09)** in terms of Behavioral Engagement. The indicator "Participating in or small group discussions", had the highest composite mean of **3.38** verbally interpreted as **Highly Engaged** while the indicator "Come to class without completing readings or assignments" had the lowest composite mean of **1.79** verbally interpreted as **Slightly Engaged**.

1.2 Cognitive Engagement

The ALS Junior High School students were **Engaged (3.16)** in terms of Cognitive Engagement. The indicator “Putting forth effort”, had the highest composite mean of **3.48** verbally interpreted as **Highly Engaged** while the indicator “Going to the professor’s office hours to review assignments of tests, or to ask questions”, had the lowest composite mean of **2.91** verbally interpreted as **Engaged**.

1.3 Emotional Engagement

The ALS Junior High School students were **Engaged (3.24)** in terms of Emotional Engagement. The indicator “Having fun in class”, had the highest composite mean of **3.47** verbally interpreted as **Highly Engaged** while the indicator “Participated in a community-based project as part of a regular course” and “Worked with faculty on activities other than course work”, had the lowest composite mean of **3.09** verbally interpreted as **Engaged**.

It can be concluded that students are emotionally engaged when they are having fun during class sessions. They feel a sense of belonging and they can express themselves, and share their thoughts and feelings with others who have the same experience as they have. Participating in community-based projects and working with teachers other than schoolwork is observed since most ALS learners are young adults. They want to have a sense of participation and a sense of usefulness in the community.

As written by Wilson (2021) in the article “Deepening Students’ Emotional Engagement”, it was now more than ever that educators needed to try to create wholesome relationships. The following list of techniques can be used in any type of classroom—virtual or physical—to increase students' emotional engagement: Every day, extend a sincere welcome to each student to reassure and inspire them, Instead of approaching students with labels or preconceptions based on past difficulties, use an assets-based approach and start over every day, To foster trust, establish a routine and consistent learning environment, Engage students and their families regularly with asset-based, positive messaging, and be willing to view progress and learning as more important than just getting the job done.

Research Question 2. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the teachers and students on student engagement level?

There was no significant difference between the responses of the groups of respondents on the mentioned variables. The generated computed probability values of Behavioral, Cognitive, and Emotional Engagement were .441, .934, and .843 respectively which were greater than the level of significance of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

The results show that the ALS junior high school learners and teachers of the Alternative Learning System have the same perception about the level of engagement among the learners. It can attest that having student engagement is an important part of a learner's learning which is a factor that makes it possible for them to learn the

competencies they should acquire. These factors greatly help students to continue and finish the program. The teacher and learner discussed the results of the Functional Literacy Test, they are encouraged to seek help from the people around them or even their employers or superiors whenever they have difficulty with the lessons.

With the help of technology, it can improve learners' independence and acquire the necessary competencies that they need. As stated in DepEd Order #013, S.2019 Procedure letter A#3, The junior high school level advanced the ALS Learners to a deeper understanding of the learning competencies that is equivalent to Grades 7 to 10. The learning competencies had a higher degree of complexity and helped learners develop an increasing degree of independence in applying knowledge, skills and values learned.

Research Question 3. What is the competence level among ALS junior high school level learners in terms of Communication skills in English, Kasanayang Pangkomunikasyon sa Filipino, Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills, Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills, Life and Career Skills, Understanding the Self and Society, and Digital Citizenship?

Table 3.1

The overall performance of Junior High School Learners in terms of Communication Skills in English was **75.07 (Developing)**. Thirteen learners were in the Advanced category, 14 were Proficient, 21 learners were in Approaching Proficiency, 13 learners were Developing, and 59 learners were under the Beginning category.

The result implies that many ALS junior high school students have difficulty when it comes to English lessons. This also shows that many students can read the word in English, but they do not understand it. Many students also have difficulty in constructing a simple sentence and at the same time, many are also shy to speak using the English language. Some learners can construct sentences, read, and speak using English. The students' limited vocabulary is the main cause of their difficulties learning English. Pupils who have a limited vocabulary often struggle with reading, writing, speaking, and listening in English. Learners who were not guided by their parents when it comes to reading and comprehension are another factor why many learners have difficulty in English subjects.

As stated in Deped Order 059 S. 2012 Implementing Guidelines on the Selection and Hiring of the ALS Literacy Volunteers, one of the qualifications needed is the ability to speak the language of the community (mother tongue/regional language).

According to Chand (2021), Poor English proficiency, underqualified teachers, a lack of logistical support, and a lack of professional development opportunities all had a detrimental influence on teaching and learning, which in turn led to students performing poorly in English.

As stated by Mckay (2023) in the article, "9 Reasons Why English is a Difficult Language to Learn", learning English is not an easy task for many students. In the English

language learners may find it difficult to learn English grammar, pronounce words correctly, remember their meanings, or employ appropriate metaphors and idioms.

Table 3.2

The overall performance of Junior High School Learners in terms of *Kasanayang Pangkomunikasyon sa Filipino* was **78.24 (Developing)**. **Twenty-one** learners were in the **Advanced category**, **13** were **Proficient**, **26** learners were **Approaching Proficient**, **16** learners were **Developing**, and **44 learners** were in the **Beginning category**.

The result implies that Filipino is not an easy subject that students do not focus on. Usually, they do not know the importance of this subject. There are words in Filipino that students are often unfamiliar with, even forming a simple sentence and using the correct method to form it.

According to the article by Gohu (2021) entitled, "These Are Why Filipino is Hard for Kids and Parents", there were several factors why Filipino was considered one of the hard subjects in the country. It is said that Filipino verbs follow a different set of rules than English verbs, making conjugation difficult, few opportunities for practice, stigma attached to the Filipino language, limited direct translation from Filipino to English, and a dearth of shows to watch while learning Tagalog.

Table 3.3

The overall performance of Junior High School Learners in terms of Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills was **72.58 (Beginning)**. **Eleven** learners were in the **Advanced category**, **25** were **Proficient**, **nine** learners were **Approaching Proficient**, **19 learners** were **Developing**, and **56 learners** were in the **Beginning category**.

The result shows that many learners are struggling when it comes to science subjects because it is in English which is one of the difficulties of the learners. Another factor that results in the poor performance of the learners in this learning strand is that from the provinces that they come from there are lack of materials and different laboratory equipment that may help the learners better understand the lesson.

According to Palines and Ortega-Dela Cruz (2021), Filipino students' science test scores were influenced by several variables, including the caliber of their teachers, the teaching-learning process, the curriculum, the instructional materials, and the administrative support.

As stated by Calleja et al. (2023) students' metacognitive reading techniques, their experiences in the classroom and at school, their motivation, their family experiences, and the resources they have at home for learning were some of these factors. Educational interventions that primarily concentrate on curriculum, instruction, and learning resources usually do not address these factors. However, the study's findings indicated that certain factors were a strong indicator of low science literacy performance, and at the absolute

least, they should assist teachers in identifying the students who were most at-risk for academic failure and required learning interventions.

Table 3.4

The overall performance of Junior High School Learners in terms of Mathematical and Problem Solving Skills was **78.60 (Developing)**. **Twenty-three** learners were in the **Advanced** category, **11** were **Proficient**, **21** learners were **Approaching Proficient**, **11** learners were **Developing**, and **44** learners were under the **Beginning** category.

It is expected that the result of the previous table and the current table are the same because they are facing the same problem in which the learner has difficulty understanding the lesson. After all, the language used is English. Students perform poorly in math subjects because they are not motivated and think it is a very challenging subject. Parents are not actively involved in their children's academic affairs, and many of them did not continue to secondary school. Poor reading comprehension has a significant impact on students, and the home environment also has an impact on students' subpar performance.

In elementary and secondary education, mathematics is an essential subject that gives students the basic knowledge and abilities to manage their lives (Ariyanti & Santoso, 2020). Regrettably, the COVID-19 pandemic has made the current state of education worse and has caused a wider disparity in math proficiency among younger pupils (Sooknanan & Seemungal, 2023). Due to potential learning gaps caused by more remediation needed by students before moving on to new lessons, the situation has resulted in a decline in math learning (Torres, 2021).

Table 3.5

The overall performance of Junior High School Learners in terms of Life and Career Skills was **86.68 (Proficient)**. **Sixty-six** learners were in the **Advanced** category, **17** were **Proficient**, **20** learners were **Approaching Proficient**, **five** learners were **Developing**, and **12** learners were under the **Beginning** category.

The result shows that the majority of the learners in ALS are adults wherein they have a lot of experience regarding various skills especially when it comes to work and livelihood. ALS students aged 16 and above have experienced different job opportunities wherein they can use these to easily understand the lessons. Through the program, they would be able to correct their lives and see a clearer direction in the future.

In today's world, life skill education must be implemented properly and with relevance. Most adult learners have a lot of experience at work and livelihood, according to ELM Learning (2022) in the article "8 Characteristics of Adult Learners Every L&D Pro Should Know", adult learners were already overburdened with responsibilities. They were more adept at multitasking than younger students and more time-selfish due to their juggling of careers, families, hobbies, health, and the home. Adults were more likely to

retain training that was pertinent and impactful if it recognized that their time was valuable and that they had a wealth of prior knowledge and experience.

Table 3.6

As to the Understanding the Self and Society, the overall performance of Junior High School Learners was **91.34 (Advanced)**. **Ninety-four (94)** learners were in the **Advanced** category, **six** were **Proficient**, **five** learners were **Approaching Proficient**, **seven** learners were **Developing**, and **eight** learners were under the **Beginning** category.

It implies that most of the ALS Junior High School learners are an advanced level in terms of understanding the self and society because they are already youths and adults that are mature and have many experiences about life and the community, they live in. They can instantly connect to what was taught since they have encountered many trials and issues throughout their lives and are aware of difficulties at an early age. In addition, because of the broad spectrum of jobs they have taken on, they are acquainted with a broad range of experiences in the community. Their understanding of the lessons will be significantly facilitated by these lived experiences.

Table 3.7

The overall performance of Junior High School Learners in terms of Digital Citizenship as **78.28 (Developing)**. **Thirty-three** learners were in the **Advanced** category, **11** were **Proficient**, **12** learners were **Approaching Proficient**, **21** learners were **Developing**, and **43** learners were under the **Beginning** category.

The outcome demonstrates that many students still have difficulty using technology, despite living in the digital age. ALS learners are left behind because the community learning centers do not have equipment that they can use and apply what is being taught. Some have available computers at home which are owned by their employers but are not allowed to use. Other students know about using desktop computers because they rent from computer shops to play games.

Research Question 4. Is there a significant relationship between student engagement and competence among ALS Junior High School level learners in Cluster 4 Calamba City?

Only Cognitive Engagement was significantly related to competence, in particular Communication Skills in English, Kasanayang Pangkomunikasyon sa Filipino, Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills, Mathematical and Problem-Solving Skills, Life and Career Skills, Understanding the Self and the Society, and Digital Citizenship with probability values of .004, .048, .000, .033, .000, and .000. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. The r values ranging from .184 to .314 were interpreted as with a low positive correlation to cognitive engagement and learning competencies. The computed probability .000,

.001, .003, .004, and .048 were lesser than the level of ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

This means that when cognitive engagement levels increase, competencies among ALS junior high school level learners also increase. This also indicates that competence and engagement are associated or connected to Communication Skills in English, Kasanayang Pangkomunikasyon sa Filipino, Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills, Mathematical and Problem Solving Skills, Life and Career Skills, Understanding the elf and Society, and Digital Citizenship.

Conclusions

1. That behavioral engagement involves giving students a voice in small group discussions, allowing them to express opinions, agree or disagree, and have their ideas heard. Students prefer to arrive prepared and study lessons sent home, promoting learning and completion. In terms of cognitive engagement, assessments made by teachers and students are equal. Even with jobs and kids, students who put in a lot of effort in the classroom are more driven to learn and finish their assigned readings. Emotional engagement in classes boosts motivation, learning rates, and retention. Students enjoy participating in extracurricular activities and working with teachers.

2. That instructors and junior high school students in ALS agree that student engagement significantly impacts their ability to learn competencies and complete the program. They discuss Functional Literacy Test results and encourage students to seek help from their peers and superiors.

3. That ALS junior high students face challenges in English lessons, science classes, and math due to language barriers and limited resources. Despite their extensive experience, they struggle with technology in the digital age.

4. That the higher the involvement of the learners, the higher the level of competence that the learners acquire.

5. That the Program PARESAN can assist students in developing self-assurance and a deeper comprehension of the material with technology and qualified teachers. Students who are exposed to the community and showcase their talents will help them grow and have the confidence to continue their journey toward achieving their goals in life.

Recommendations

1. Learners may not focus only on classroom settings to learn more about their behavior. They may also be exposed to different extracurricular activities to develop their positive attitudes not only inside the community learning centers but also in the

community. With the help of different activities, they may apply what they have learned inside the CLC and be a useful citizen. To broaden learners' cognitive engagement, they may be involved in different games, arts and crafts, gardening, word games that are interactive, activities involving recall, reflection, and discussion, and talks in groups and instructional lectures. To further develop positive attitudes, learners may expose themselves even outside their community by joining school activities such as tree planting, sports activities, activities showcasing their talents, etc.

2. Learners' motivation to finish their education in ALS may be assessed to develop their deep understanding based on the assessment of teachers and students for further improvement. In this way, learners will be able to acknowledge their strengths.

3. English and Filipino communication may be exercised at home and inside the community learning centers without hesitation. Learners are encouraged to read English and Filipino stories and articles in books, newspapers, social media platforms, and the like. With the help of technology, they can easily learn the correct pronunciation and meaning of the unfamiliar words that they may encounter. In dealing with Mathematics and Scientific and Critical Thinking Skills, these two are interrelated in terms of their weaknesses, it is better also to seek feedback or suggestions coming from their superiors/employers in dealing with math and critical thinking problems. Small group discussions or collaborative works are also encouraged where learners can seek help from their peers. The teacher can also send video tutorials on solving the different math problems. Learners need hard work to process this kind of learning and should not rely on traditional teaching techniques and use differentiated ways of learning the lessons. Change their mindset that math and science are difficult subjects but rather boost their abilities to respond, solve, and attend to the different problems that they may encounter in the said learning strands. Engage in different problem-solving that can develop creativity and information processing in solving until it can generate answers.

For the Life and Career Skills, since it is already advanced, they must exercise these life and career skills on a higher level of activities like venturing into leadership. For them to test their communication, training, and job shadowing these will help to explore the future nearly with people who have the experience to guide them.

Though the result shows an advanced level when it comes to Understanding the Self and Society, this must be monitored that lead them to develop other potentials and enable them to live in the context of family and local community that provides practical options to the existing ALS regulations. This will serve better improvement in their life, employability, and livelihood as one of the competencies of ALS in the Department of Education.

Help from different private sectors for the donation of computers in the community learning centers that will be used for hands-on classes for LS6 Digital Citizenship. Local Government Units may create an E-library in the community may be sought so that resident ALS learners can utilize the use of computers for the improvement and application of their learning. To gather data communication, learn digital etiquette, and engage in digital media and social posts. Learn how to protect privacy, avoid over-haring, think before posting, check if all information comes from, and most of all information literacy.

4. Teachers and learners may work together to raise the level of competencies among ALS junior high school level. Learners are encouraged to attend class sessions

regularly for them to get the necessary competencies that they need to be able to pass the A&E Test. Close monitoring of learners' attendance and performance during the learning sessions, home visitation, and coordination with parents or guardians.

5. Implementation of Project PARESAN to help learners gain confidence and a better understanding of the lessons with the help of technology and equipped teachers. Exposing learners to the community and showcasing their talents would develop a sense of belongingness and being proud of themselves because they can show what they've got.

6. Future researchers may conduct a more in-depth study about this to pay more attention to things that can help the Alternative Learning System learners in the Division of Calamba City.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that ethical principles were properly followed at every step of the research procedure. Through a Consent Form, the respondents were fully informed of the inquest's goals. Through the letter, students were made aware of the task they would be completing for the study to be successful. Additionally, it was made clear that they would not be required to participate in the survey, especially if it was done against their will. To protect the respondents' identities and maintain the confidentiality of the data, the collected questionnaires were handled appropriately. Likewise, the researcher was accountable for the collected data of the respondents. The works of various bodies were also acknowledged and cited in this study. Even though the results defied the accepted standards, it was still reported honestly.

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REFERENCES

- Ariyanti, G., & Santoso, E. (2020). Addressing Students Learning Gaps in Mathematics through Differentiated Instruction. *Journal on Mathematics Education*, 11(2), 209-222. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1252002.pdf#:~:text=URL%3A%20https%3A%2F%2Ffiles.eric.ed.gov%2Ffulltext%2FEJ1252002.pdf%0AVisible%3A%200%25%20>
- Calleja et al. (2023). Addressing the Poor Science Performance of Filipino Learners: Beyond Curricular and Instructional Interventions Beyond Curricular and Instructional Interventions. *Animo Repository | De La Salle University Research*. https://animorepository.dlsu.edu.ph/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1087&context=res_aki
- Chatti, A. (2021, June 2). Students engagement: Challenges and solutions. *K12 Digest*. <https://www.k12digest.com/students-engagement-challenges-and-solutions/>
- ELM Learning. (2022, February 11). 8 Characteristics of Adult Learners Every L&D Pro Should Know. *ELM Learning*. <https://elmlearning.com/blog/8-characteristics-of-adult-learners-every-ld-pro-should-know/>
- Gamboa, R. (2023, January 18). Second chance for school dropouts. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.philstar.com/business/2023/01/19/2238514/second-chance-school-dropouts>
- Gohu, K. (2021, August 19). These are why Filipino is hard for kids and parents. *Modern Parenting*. <https://modernparenting-onemega.com/5-reasons-why-filipino-is-hard-for-kids-and-parents/>
- Lee et al. (2019, February 14). Exploring factors, and indicators for measuring students' sustainable engagement in E-Learning. *MDPI*. <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/11/4/985>
- Palines and O Palines, K., & Ortega-Dela Cruz, R. (2021). Ej1327860. *ERIC - Education Resources Information Center*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1327860>
- Sooknanan & Seemungal. (2023). Digital inclusion as a social determinant of health. *PhilArchive: The Philosophy E-Print Archive*. <https://philarchive.org/archive/AGUASL-2>
- Sukor et al. (2021). Relationship Between Students' Engagement with Academic Performance Among Non-Food Science Students Enrolled in Food Science Course. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1339459.pdf>
- Torres, R. (2021, June). Addressing the Learning Gaps in the Distance Learning Modalities. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352551820_Addressing_the_Learning_Gaps_in_the_Distance_Learning_Modalities